

Effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases at selected hospitals.

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ABSTRACT: -

INTRODUCTION: This study investigates the Effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases at selected hospitals.

METHOD: - Used quantitative research approach. Quasi experimental non -randomized control group design was used. 60 samples were selected using a non- probability convenient sampling technique. The accessible population consisted of patients with lower respiratory tract diseases. As intervention respiratory care bundle implemented, it was evident that the respiratory care bundle is significantly effective in reducing dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.

RESULT: -

Findings related to level of dyspnea before implementation of respiratory care bundle:

In the experimental group, 36.7% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 63.3% of them had severe dyspnea. In the control group, 43.3% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 56.7% of them had severe dyspnea.

Findings related to level of dyspnea after implementation of respiratory care bundle:

In the experimental group, in the pretest, 36.7% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 63.3% of them had severe dyspnea. In the post-test, 40% of them had mild dyspnea, 53.3% of them had moderate dyspnea and 6.7% of them had severe dyspnea. In the control group, in the pretest, 43.3% of the patients with lower respiratory tract

diseases had moderate dyspnea and 56.7% of them had severe dyspnea. In the post-test, 20% of them had mild dyspnea, 36.7% of them had moderate dyspnea and 43.3% of them had severe dyspnea.

Findings related to Paired t-test for the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases:

The average dyspnea score in the pretest was 6.8 which reduced to 4.3 in the post-test. The t-value for this test was 10.6 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected.

CONCLUSION:

The study established the respiratory care bundle's positive impact on the dyspnea level among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases. The findings emphasize the importance of targeted interventions in enhancing dyspnea among this population. This research contributes to our understanding of the effectiveness of respiratory care bundles on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases at selected hospitals.

KEYWORDS: Respiratory care bundle, dyspnea, and lower respiratory tract diseases.

INTRODUCTION:

Nursing is both an art and a science providing care with compassion, regard for each patient's dignity, and an artistic touch. It is founded on a corpus of knowledge that is always evolving due to discoveries and inventions. When providing nursing care, we should be mindful, operate in a regular, routine manner, and apply the fundamentals of good nursing practice.[1]

The process of gas exchange between blood and atmospheric air, and later between blood and bodily cells, is called respiration. Breathed air travels via the airways to the lungs, where it is cleaned, moisturized, and saturated with water vapor as dust particles adhere to the mucus that coats the lining membrane. It is also warmed or chilled to body temperature.[2]

Lung abscesses, pneumonia, Tuberculosis (TB), bronchitis, and bronchiolitis are examples of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI). While many LRTIs are infectious and caused by viruses, some have bacterial roots. LRTIs are the most common cause of death worldwide among all infections and are characterized by symptoms such as coughing, weakness, fever, lethargy, tightness in the chest, and shortness of breath or dyspnea. In younger children, up to 90% of LRTIs were caused by viral infections. Acute lower respiratory tract infections (ALRTI) are a major cause of death for children under the age of five, whereas lower respiratory tract infections account for over 11.9 million hospitalizations of young children worldwide. Pus or fluid accumulates in the lung's alveoli as a result of pneumonia. Pneumonia is the leading cause of death for children under five years old worldwide. The swelling or inflammation of the bronchial tubes is known as bronchitis. Influenza seasonally impacts the upper and lower respiratory systems.[3]

The World Health Organisation recommends immunization against influenza and pneumococcus, however effective policy formation in this area is hampered by the absence of reliable data on the incidence and etiology of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) in India. No research has used longitudinal follow-up to evaluate the burden of LRTI among older individuals living in the community in India. Since 13% of the world's population was 60 years of age or over in 2017, data from India is necessary for any reliable assessment of the burden of LRTI worldwide. To gather data on the prevalence and viral etiology of LRTI, World Health Organization (WHO) therefore formed a dynamic cohort of older persons (60 years of age and older) who lived in a community in rural north India.[4]

In India, lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) acquired in the community are frequently the cause of death for senior citizens. Up till now, hospital-based research on the bacterial etiology

of LRTIs in older individuals has been done in India. The incidence and etiology of LRTI are likely to be overestimated in hospital-based research because many patients in this age range have limited access to hospitals. In this age group, a significant number of LRTIs are linked to viruses. There is not enough data available on the prevalence and viral etiology of LRTI in older individuals in India. There were no studies from India included in recent systematic reviews on viral etiologic agents of acute respiratory infections (ARI) in older adults or hospitalization linked to community-acquired pneumonia.

LRTI among older adults is predicted to become a major public health issue in India as the percentage of older adults rises along with life expectancy. In India, the National Programme for the Healthcare of the Elderly (NPHCE) was established to offer senior citizens comprehensive preventative treatment as well as health promotion. The World Health Organisation recommends immunization against influenza and pneumococcus, however effective policy formation in this area is hampered by the absence of reliable data on the incidence and etiology of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) in India. As far as we are aware, no research has used longitudinal follow-up to evaluate the burden of LRTI among older individuals living in the community in India.[5]

METHODS:

Study Design: Quasi experimental non -randomized control group design.[6]

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.[7]

Setting: Selected hospitals of the city [8]

Sampling Technique: Non probability, convenient sampling technique.[9]

Population: Patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.[10]

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention (Respiratory care bundle). Post-intervention on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases were assessed. The data was collected from 05/01/2025 to 24/01/2025.

Data collection:

Section A: Semi-Structured Interviewing Questionnaire will be prepared by the investigator, which includes questions regarding demographic variables: Age, Gender, Educational status, Occupation, Duration of illness, Family history of respiratory diseases, Family income per month, Personal habits, Health habits, and Diagnosis.

Section B: A table of Modified Borg Dyspnea Scale

The Modified Borg Dyspnea Scale is a tool used to assess the level of dyspnea, or shortness of breath, experienced by a patient. It is a subjective measure, where the patient rates their perceived level of breathlessness on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 being no breathlessness and 10 being maximal breathlessness. Further, describe the difficulty of breathing and rate the described level of dyspnea under the grading categorized with score key and score grading between 1 to 4 i.e., no evidence of dyspnea, mild dyspnea, moderate dyspnea, and severe dyspnea respectively.

Method of data collection:

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct research were obtained.
2. The purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was obtained from the participants.
4. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority.
5. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using a non-probability convenient sampling technique.
6. Informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better cooperation during the data collection.
7. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data were discussed.
8. The data gathering process began on 05/01/2025 to 24/01/2025.
9. Given a prepared tool containing
 - Section A - Consent form
 - Section B - Tool for demographic variables.
 - Section C - observational checklist of level of dyspnea.
10. Assessed level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.

11. Implemented respiratory care bundle on patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.
12. Post-tests were collected on 3 days of intervention.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the pre-test and post-test scores.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases. Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in dyspnea score among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases in experimental and control group. Fisher's exact test for the association between dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases and selected demographic variables.

Data analysis:

Sample Size: The formula used for sample size is-

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

n = sample size

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ = Critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (1.96)

MOE = Margin of error (0.16)

P = Sample Proportion (0.248)

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

$$n = 1.96^2 * 0.248 * (1-0.248) / 0.16^2$$

$$n = 3.84 * 0.248 * 0.752 / 0.025$$

$$n = 0.716 / 0.025$$

$$n = 28.6$$

For the study sample size will be 60, experimental group (n =30) and a control group (n =30).[11]

Eligibility Criteria:[12]**Inclusive criteria:** Patients who are

- diagnosed with lower respiratory tract diseases
- able to perform spirometer exercises
- willing to participate in the study
- able to understand Marathi and English language

Exclusive criteria: Patients who are

- unstable
- having comorbidities with cardiac, renal disease and recent surgeries

Withdrawal criteria:

- The sample can withdraw from research at any point of time during the data collection.

RESULT:**Finding related to demographic characteristics of the participants.**

Age: In an experimental group, 23.3% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases were in the age group of 21-30 years, 26.7% of them were in the age group of 30.1-40 years, 30% of them were in the age group of 40.1-50 years and 20% of them were in the age group of 50.1-60 years. In the control group, 26.7% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases were in the age group of 21-30 years, 30% of them were in the age group of 30.1-40 years, 23.3% of them were in the age group of 40.1-50 years and 20% of them were in the age group of 50.1-60 years.

Gender: In an experimental group, 50% of them were males and 50% of them were females. In the control group, 36.7% of them were males and 63.3% of them were females.

Educational status: In an experimental group, 13.3% of them had no formal education, 26.7% of them had primary education, 36.7% of them had higher secondary education and 23.3% of them had graduated. In the control group, 13.3% of them had no formal education, 26.7% of

them had primary education, 33.3% of them had higher secondary education and 26.7% of them had graduated.

Occupation: In the experimental group, 20% of them had private jobs, 26.7% of them had government jobs, 10% of them were homemakers, 30% of them were laborers/daily wagers and 13.3% of them were unemployed. In the control group, 23.3% of them had private jobs, 26.7% of them had government jobs, 3.3% of them were homemakers, 40% of them were laborers/daily wagers and 6.7% of them were unemployed.

Family income per month: In the experimental group, 46.7% of them had a family monthly income less than Rs.10000, and 23.3% of them had a family monthly income of RS. 10001-15000, 16.7% of them had a monthly family income of Rs. 15001-20000, and 13.3% of them had a monthly family income more than Rs. 20000. In the control group, 43.3% of them had a family monthly income less than Rs.10000, 33.3% of them had family monthly income RS. 10001-15000, 13.3% of them had a monthly family income of Rs. 15001-20000, and 10% had a monthly family income of more than Rs. 20000.

Duration of illness: In the experimental group, 56.7% of them had an illness for less than 6 months, 36.7% of them had the illness for 6 months to 1 year and 6.7% of them had the illness for more than 1 year. In the control group, 50% of them had an illness for less than 6 months, 43.3% of them had illness for 6 months to 1 year and 6.7% of them had the illness for more than one year.

Family history of respiratory disease: In the experimental group, 13.3% had a family history of respiratory diseases. 13.3% of them had asthma. In the control group, 16.7% had a family history of respiratory diseases. 16.7% of them had asthma.

Personal habits: In the experimental group, 56.7% of them did not have any personal habits, 30% of them had a habit of tobacco chewing, and 13.3% of them had a habit of cigarette smoking. In the control group, 50% of them did not have any personal habits, 40% of them had a habit of tobacco chewing, and 10% of them had a habit of cigarette smoking.

Health habits: In the experimental group, 6.7% of them had a habit of meditation, 73.3% of them had a habit of brisk walking and 20% of them had exercises. In the control group, 10% of them had a habit of meditation, 70% of them had a habit of brisk walking and 20% of them had exercises.

Diagnosis: In the experimental group, 16.7% of them had asthma, 33.3% of them had bronchitis, 20% of them were diagnosed with tuberculosis, 20% of them were diagnosed with pneumonia and 10% of them were diagnosed with chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases. In the control group, 13.3% of them had asthma, 23.3% of them had bronchitis, 23.3% of them were diagnosed with tuberculosis, 23.3% of them were diagnosed with pneumonia and 16.7% of them were diagnosed with chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases.

Finding related to dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases before implementation of respiratory care bundle in both experimental and control group

In the experimental group, 36.7% of the patients with lower respiratory tract group, 43.3% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 56.7% had severe dyspnea.

Finding related to the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases

In the experimental group, in the pretest, 36.7% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 63.3% of them had severe dyspnea. In the post-test, 40% of them had mild dyspnea, 53.3% of them had moderate dyspnea and 6.7% of them had severe dyspnea. In the control group, in the pretest, 43.3% of the patients with lower respiratory tract diseases had moderate dyspnea and 56.7% had severe dyspnea. In the post-test, 20% of them had mild dyspnea, 36.7% of them had moderate dyspnea and 43.3% of them had severe dyspnea. This indicates that dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases improved remarkably after the respiratory care bundle.

Paired t-test for the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases:

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases. The average dyspnea score in the pretest was 6.8 which reduced to 4.3 in the post-test. The t-value for this test was 10.6 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average dyspnea score in the post-test was significantly less than in the pretest. The respiratory care bundle is significantly effective in reducing dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.

Two-sample z-test for the comparison of the change in dyspnea score among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases in experimental and control groups:

The researcher applied a two-sample z-test for the comparison of reduction in dyspnea score among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases in experimental and control group. The average reduction in dyspnea score in the experimental group was 2.5 which was 1.3 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 5.2. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in dyspnea score in the control group was significantly less than in the experimental group. The respiratory care bundle is significantly effective in reducing dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.

Since p-values corresponding to occupation, family income per month, Family history of respiratory occupation, family income per month, Family history of respiratory diseases and Diagnosis were found to have a significant association with dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases.

1. Comparison with Effectiveness of Incentive Spirometry and Deep Breathing Exercises in Reducing Dyspnea in Patients with COPD

- Similarities:
 - Same target symptom: dyspnea.
 - Intervention includes incentive spirometry and deep breathing.
- Differences:
 - Excludes oral care.
 - Focused only on COPD, not a broad group of LRTDs.

2. Comparison with Oral Care Practices and Prevention of Respiratory Infections in Hospitalized Patients

- Similarities:

- Oral care as a preventive measure.
- Hospitalized respiratory patients.
- Differences:
 - Focused more on infection prevention (like VAP), not dyspnea directly

3. Comparison with Effectiveness of Respiratory Therapy Bundle in Reducing Breathlessness in Pneumonia Patients

- Similarities:
 - Same interventions: oral care, IS, DBE.
 - Targeted pneumonia patients.
- Differences:
 - Smaller sample size.
 - Used only Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for dyspnea.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.
- A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized.
- The study can be replicated in different settings.
- The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study.
- An experimental study can be performed using different types of interventions.
- A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.

ABBREVIATIONS:

1. TB: Tuberculosis
2. LRTI: Lower respiratory tract infections
3. ALRTI: Acute lower respiratory tract infections
4. WHO: World Health Organization

5. ARI: Acute respiratory infections
6. NPHCE: National Programme for the Healthcare of the Elderly
7. IS: Incentive spirometry
8. DBE: Deep breathing exercises
9. VAS: Visual Analog Scale

Table 1.1: Dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases before implementation of respiratory care bundle in both experimental and control group

n=30, 30

Dyspnea	Experimental		Control	
	Pretest		Pretest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
No evidence	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate	11	36.7%	13	43.3%
Severe	19	63.3%	17	56.7%

Table 2.1: Effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases

n=30, 30

Dyspnea	Experimental				Control			
	Pretest		Post-test		Pretest		Post-test	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
No evidence	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	0	0.0%	12	40.0%	0	0.0%	6	20.0%
Moderate	11	36.7%	16	53.3%	13	43.3%	11	36.7%
Severe	19	63.3%	2	6.7%	17	56.7%	13	43.3%

Table 2.2: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of respiratory care bundle on the level of dyspnea among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases

n=30, 30

	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p-value
Pretest	6.8	1.2	10.6	29	0.000
Post-test	4.3	1.3			

Table 2.3: Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in dyspnea score among patients with lower respiratory tract diseases in experimental and control group

n=30, 30

Group	Mean	SD	Z	p-value
Experimental	2.5	1.3	5.2	0.000
Control	1.0	0.9		

Fig no.1: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of pre-test dyspnea in experimental and control groups.

Fig no.2: Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of pre-test and post-test dyspnea in experimental and control group

Fig no.3: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average dyspnea score in pre-test and post-test in the experimental group.

Fig no.4: Bar diagram showing distribution of average reduction in dyspnea score in experimental and control group

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